

Negative Child Behaviors and Adult Anxiety Association

Sarah Arif

Department of English writing and communication,

Forman Christian College, University Lahore

WRCM 102: Writing & communication II

Section EE

Instructor: Alvina Wasim

June 20,2020

Abstract

The short term anxieties are important to be measured in order to avoid its greater afterword impacts on individual's mentality. These short term apprehensions cause distraction, restlessness, agitation, and behavioral occurrences etc. To enumerate individual's anxiety, I will specifically use child misbehavior as objective and the study of outcome of those behaviors in adult perceivers as subjective. The Freud's objective theory demonstrated the role of physical factors including behaviors to cause anxiety in individual. The purpose is to explore the rate of anxiety supporting his after early theory, the adult perceivers who undergo apprehensive emotional, behavioral changes caused by child misbehaviors. The signaling anxiety signs in adult perceiver proved the intensity of their abomination in survey.

Keywords; Children, Negative behaviors, physical perception, Anxiety Association, perceptive behavioral occurrence.

Introduction;

The main purpose of this paper is exploring and bridging psychological gap in studies where theorists explain efficiently why and in which situations children behave disruptively?, but how other experience their misbehavior, is so limited in research works. I would be trying to explain the adult acrimony as a primary emotion and its conversion to anxiety based on tense surrounding. The introductory section will recover the basic explanation of behavior and anxiety as thus; The morpheme ism makes words more distinctive and particular in practice (Graham, 2019). Behaviorism in respect to its nature is a tangled tale. It deals with the stimulus-response relationship that is based on measurable observed behaviors. J.B. Watson (1878-58) was attributed to be the founder of behaviorism. Modern behaviorists have been studying observable actions sophisticatedly but this is my own opinion that any behavior that creates unscrupulous and vexatious environment is an asocial negative behavior and its definition in judging child behaviors is different. Deborah Hage quoted that the; “children behave the way they behave because they think the way they think.” This quote discloses the truthiness that children are not to be blamed for what they have done anger causing because they are unintentionally doing it.

Freeman (Freeman, 2012) suggested anxiety is derived from German word “Angh” which means press down, load, to strangle etc. Shanaz (Shahnaz, 2012,) proposed that anxiety refers to unpleasant sense of fear and restlessness. (Pg. 51). Anxiety is a prolonged discussed term which has been the matter of numberless researches till now. I will be supporting my article using Freud’s(1856) after early theory of anxiety explaining significant role of objectivity of

anxiety along with giving a less assistance to restoration of foregoing experiences. The research question for this study will be;

Do perception of negative child behaviors causes anxiety in adults of Pakistan?

These objectives can be identified in research paper:

Can certain change in environment cause restlessness if yes then it is the part of anxiety.

Do behavioral negativity triggers anxiety in perceivers?

It would be able to develop personal understanding and at least provide basic information in relation to physical environment and mental impatience or relationship of unconscious child behavior and its substandard impacts on adult perceivers.

Literature Review:

The objective of this proposal is to explain objectivity of anxiety and its relationship with perception and environment. To find this, a literature is required to be reviewed on these areas: Freud's middle theory of objective anxiety and origination of his views other than libido and repression, Perception, subjective anxiety and role of existentialism. There is no need to explain why children are behaving the way they should not because it has already been recovered in theories. The purpose is to observe the challenging anxiety issues in adults no matter if its timely apprehension and not a disorder but there is need to amplify environmental and neurotic impacts of child misbehaviors that lead to short term anxiety signs and antagonism in adults. These parts of literature will be covering the unpleasant circumstances and its ramification of anxiety.

Adult's treating children, knowing and underpinning their debilitated sense of morality. Several past studies have extensively reported the deep rooted findings on objectivity of anxiety, but less well has researched and explained association of anxiety followed by misbehaviors in children This research relies upon anxiety and its entanglement with environmental factors to influence

behaviors. However this phenomenon may be investigated as sudden episodic disposition of situational anxiety by perception. This framework has been concerning ones behavioral impact on others, by specifically studying the relationship of child disorderly conducted behaviors with adult's acrimony and conversion of anxiety based on ongoing tensed situations. This literature is divided into three subdivision as; 1) Freud's objective theory of Anxiety which will illustrate his views and relationship of environmental stimulus or behaviors to anxiety. 2) This part had been covered other behavioral occurrences (perceiver as adults) during child situational misbehaving or unaccepted manners. 3) Third and last part is interested to define the child misbehaviors as deviant or orthodox choosing one of two, by supplementing their deprived development during childhood.

Freud's Objective views of Anxiety:

In my examination of Freud's (1856) theories on anxiety, I could found that objective perspectives of anxiety are best displayed by him in comparison to his classical and libidinal based work. Morris (Morris, 1973) has described Freud's (1856) objective theory as his middle theory, which elucidated that anxiety is the result of outside occasions and dangers that are learnt. Here is a question to raise, can we feel anxiety even when we have experienced that same event and is having knowledge about? The comeback may or may not be true but Guinot et al. (2011) described anxiety as an unfocused sentiment towards concrete situation which is not based on its past involvement. But this is my own opinion that individual's anxiety is not based on his experiences, its occurrence is indeterminate as brain can release serotonin, dopamine and norepinephrine anytime which may result to anxiety, but it is penetrable that neophyte may get more commotion than experienced person. For example; unmannered children in family may be escalating less uneasiness because of their recurrent behaviors seem normal, but it may be quiet

apprehensive and agitated for neophytes having no young children in family tree. Freud (1856) in his middle theory still connecting neurotic repression and libidinal trouble with objective anxiety. He opined that restraint occasions together with controlled execution of acts causes anxiety (Morris, 1973). He also demonstrated that anxiety creates repression, it comes about after we experience external events, as internal factors may be less anxiety causing than external ones. In other words perceptual anxiety has more grounded impacts to create individual stressed. An individual cannot feel on edge until he will not be getting any boots through his faculties, from environment. Freud's classical theory demonstrated that human perception is immaculate, for him neurosis caused distorted perception that was why he did not elaborate the role of environment deliberately but where there be perception there will be senses and these have close relationship with environment, though Freud's classical psychoanalysis has been focusing neurotic outcome rather than environmental contribution to it. The specificity of this research is to examine child misbehaviors which are perceived by youngsters and their association of anxiety with these objective misbehaviors and adult reactions towards the situation to deal with it. Crosby(1976) initialized that no single person has proved anxiety at best to be internalized conflict. There are certain environmental and objective facts to commence anxiety and it might or not be the product of repression. Crosby(1976) illustrated Freud's apprehension as real and objective anxiety which is typical, normal, and valuable utilitarian dilemma. Graham George (Graham, 2019) manifested three types of behaviorisms one out of which is analytical or logical behaviorism that pedagogically cruces individualistic environmental interactionism rather than internal situation or condition. Graham mentioned that when individuals are in trouble they are characterized with external accomplished situation rather

than knowing their internal neuroticism.

Behavioral occurrence during misbehaving situations:

When children perform misbehaviors they do not only define their own behavior but give rise to other behaviors around them. The dynamic situation will give rise to two types of behaviors; firstly misbehaviors that children are executing, second; the adult behavior or their reaction towards child misbehavior. Adult reactions may be aggressive, polite, cringy, jaw clenching and others. These all are outcomes of anxiety. Vynner (2018) opined that anxiety provokes violent and aggressive responses but this may be an issue of few individuals. Sidnam (1964) notified that anxiety is incomprehensible to characterize because it is crippling individuals to perform versatile behaviors in suspension to everyone is possessing idiosyncratic personality and, they are having their own way to respond and deal with anxiety no matter if what is the source of anxiety. Carl et,al(2004) expounded Tillich's views on distinction of stimulus for fear and anxiety which means objectives of both terms are different in nature. Heshmat (2018) presented Horwitz's association of specified things and objects to detect fear. He opined Anxiety is an emotional state which is result of boredom, doubt, mental conflict, disappointment and bashfulness. Here I go, the state of anxiety resulted because of misbehaving, is not encountering fear, it emerges as short term apprehension of disappointment, disobedience and intensively created environmental disturbance by children, they may shout, perform irrelevant actions, may use cursive or restricted words, perform obsessive behaviors, play with noisy electronic devices etc. Children are naughty small human beings who are having no better understanding and developed morality at that stage. They are learners and imitators. Parents may sometime get offended over their misdoings and beat them which are the reactions that come out after one feels excessive anxiety. This is the violent reaction of caregivers towards child misbehaving but

initially this reaction might be rationally offended. Misbehaviors generate moderate tense environment, as restriction of desired action towards specific behavior causes anxiety and mental, physical acrimony as the prime response (newwenhuuys, Oudejans. 2011). All kind of behaviors are objective and when perceived result to specific kind of emotional state which is mostly anxiety for undesirable dilemmas. Unpleasant circumstances, events, behaviors cause anxiety which is enunciated with admirable clarity.

Child Insolent behaviors neither deviant nor orthodox;

As it is perspicuous that every different or unacceptable behavior is considered as deviant behavior but, every different and unacceptable behavior is not deviant. Likewise child's negative behaviors are unacceptable and different than fully-fledged adults but their behaviors are not deviant, owing to the fact these behaviors are unacceptable but tolerated with conscious mindfulness compromising their declined superego development. Levin(2010) proposed the term Living in alternative reality, which divided into two basic parts for misbehavior toleration, Its reality and alternative reality. Our tolerant and habitual reactions towards child misbehaviors are reality and the steps to recover misbehaviors by teaching them moral values are alternative reality. Misbehaviors generate moderately tense environment which is not the matter to blame children. Deborah Hage has cited this term exceptionally that "children behave the way they behave because they think the way they think"! Which means children are not just poor morally developed but poor cognitively developed, the bona fide development is required to reach the best defined demeanor and thinking styles. The over headed reviews had been accomplished to understand and prove the relationship of objective misbehaviors and subjective anxiety as the outcome of unpleasant perception.

Research Methodology;

The specification of this research emphasis on literate adult association of anxiety with negative child behaviors in Pakistani adults. The questionnaire survey was online administered to population sample of random people including males and females belonging to different age groups from 18 to 25. The focus of designed questionnaire was to determine the rate of anxiety, which is defined as a state of restlessness by Shahnaz (Shahnaz, 2012), in adults by perception of child odd behaviors and their experiences with that awful episode.

When we perceive something we are experiencing it, by using our own comprehensive ability to interpret schematic data. The aim of questionnaire was attitudinal interrogation, concerning adult anxiety in their perception and experience of negative child behavior. The questions related to respondent's deliberate botheredness and their offensive experience with child was solicited. The survey was conducted on 22 respondents based on the sampling population in respect to their ethnic, social, educational, religious and aging differences.

The following steps were taken into consideration in methodological approach;

The list of questions was organized and participants were invited using online sources to fill in the survey queries. Respondents belonging to different educational status, sexes and ages were participating and data was collected in automated fashion by questionnaire administration. Lastly, data table was illustrated statistically to manifest the results as a percentage in terms of gender and age based participation of respondents.

The table indicated below demonstrated the gender and age of respondents in statistical manner.

Participants (Ps)	Age		Gender			Total
	18-20	21-25	Female	male	Anonymous	
	11Ps	11Ps	11	8	3	
Percentage	50%	50%	50%	36%	14%	100%

Conceptual Framework;

Classical psychoanalytic theory paid not much attention to environment, though it focused on unconscious repression and libido conflict to explain anxiety. Freud(1856-1939) believed that a person feels anxious when lack contentment and then conflict arise between three levels of mind. Freud did not consider environmental impacts for the person to feel anxiety, but the

central focus of this research is his objective theory to find the gap of child behaviors on the people that bother them because perception is experience which we learnt through environmental interaction. Though when we perceive something negative it drag into unfortunate experience and bitterness which then lead to anxiety.

Data Analysis & discussion;

Presentation of Age statistics in graph;

Presentation of data analysis and discussion will be specifically proving the agitation rate which is defined as anxiety, caused by child misbehaviors. Their misbehaviors as anxiety causing, and the adults, suffering the situation and dealing with it. Turn your focus on graph below;

This graph displays the age specific partition rate of respondents, as the focus of research was to explore agitation specifically in adults. The estimation of people belonging to age 18 and over, contemplated to be adults forever and day. The survey was administered to 22 participants from the age groups of 18 to 25 which illustrate the exact criteria of adult age in this research. Age was one of the basic requirements of research question; the graph is presented to prove the limitations and authenticity of research question.

Presentation of Gender statistics in pie chart;

Questionnaire was handed out to all people regardless of their genders to collect the dissimilar views, if present. Percentage of participants has been depicted above that determines the number of 50% of females participated in the survey queries, 36 percent of respondents were males and 14% of them did not mention their identities. The aftermath calculations have shown the rate of agitation and teaching morality to children almost the same in both genders. Bundle of other researches have proved masculinity as aggressive in most cases in comparison to femininity but in this research male and females both tried to cooperate with children knowing their inappropriate behavior, the result of their superego lack. However there are not many differences found in genders on behalf of dealing with children and situation in spite of that

rate of agitation, restlessness, worry, mentally conflicted, distraction and anxiety were found floating through their mind to behavior that is specific and learnt.

Question 1: Have you ever perceive children behaving in a negative way?

Here the explanation is clear, the pie chart shows the 45.5% of people often perceive children misbehaving, 36.4 percent of them perceive them sometime performing odd behaviors and 9.1% of them always perceive them doing misbehaviors, however 9.1% of population has never seen them doing misbehaviors. Approximately 91% of people have perceived children behaving inappropriately to some extent, only the ration of 9.1% people have never perceive them behaving in negative way. The answers had proved that children perform unsuitable behaviors which are perceived by adults at different ratios.

Question 2: Have you ever feel bothered when you see children behaving in an asocial way?

The above manifested chart has shown that all the participants undergo disturbance and inconvenience when they see children behaving disruptively. Statistics has proved 50.1% of people occasionally bothered by misbehaving patterns, 22.7% of them reported frequent detection, feeling of worry and 18.2% of them always feel restless when they see children misbehaving. The figure shows no rates about people who do not get bothered by children when they behave the way they do. The last options were not answered by people as it is intelligible that everyone gets bothered by child negative attitudes but the quantity of agitation may differ from person to person.

Question 3: To what extent you feel anxious/restlessness when children disobey you?

31.8 percent of people has reported that they always feel restlessness when children disobeys them, 40.9% of results have shown people to be in restless state on every so often. 9.1% of them feel restless more often. However 18.2% of ration has never felt mental conflict when a child disobeys them. It has been featured in the framework that the people, who do not feel restless when child disobeys them and do other uncertain behaviors, are habitual to situations because of their persistent acknowledgement of specific behavior no matter if it's appropriate or not.

Question 4: Do you feel uneasiness when children throw tantrum?

It is obvious to feel ill at ease when children throw tantrum, when they particularly throw tantrum they create very bad and anxious environment for others. Above figured chart demonstrated that 18.2 percent of people will always feel uncomfortable when children will made loud proxysm of weeping. 50% of people will sometime go through uncomfortableness because of this disgusting emotion and 18.2% of them always and 13.6% of them often withstand disgust. 4.5% of people are not sure of their reaction towards child tantrums as illustrated above. Some extent of restlessness has been found at fluctuation in different people.

Question 5: To what extent you feel your surrounding most anxiety causing because of child misbehavior?

The percentage of 22.7 people had revealed that whenever children perform negative acts, at everytime they tolerate anxiety while 18.2 percent of people are not prone to such situation at regular basis but suffers sometime, other 40.9% of them have mentioned their experience as not on regular basis but at few occasional moments. Only 13.8% of them had repoted that they will never feel their surrounding as disturbed and restless if children will be misbehaving

and, 4.5% of the population is not sure or would be having no experience to such situation, in other words.

Question 6: Would you feel distract when children will perform hitting and beating actions around you?

The pie chart above has been clearly indicating that everytime children performs violent and noise causing action, 63.6% of people surrounded them will feel distracted. 22.7 % people not at regular basis suffer distraction and 9.1 percent of them will never be distracted to situation. However 4.5 percentage shows often distracted rates in people. Distraction means sowing seeds for uplifting of anxiety, it can be very prime emotion of an individual to raise anxiety. The charted data above has emplified the estimation of 90% people who were distracted by children.

Question 7; Would you feel aggressive if child will disobey you?

Aggressiveness might be called as seconday emotion which takes place after extensive anxiety. First person feels anxious and then they turn to aggression as repercussion of anxiety

is aggression. Here we go to chart calculations that has elaborated 27.3% of people always get aggressive towards child disobedience, 27.3% people occasionally get aggressive not everytime and 18.2% of them not more than sometime do, 13.8% of ration had never been aggressive to disobedience while 13.8% are not sure for what the outcome of their emotions can be.

Question 8: Would you feel your surrounding distract or anxiety causing when children will perform odd behaviors and make noise?

Noise is extremely distracted, when children shout out loud, play with noisy devices it may distracted people and make them feel more restless. This noise may be intermittent, continuous and impulsive. It depends on situation and internity of children. The chart represented that odd performances of children always make 27.3% people anxious and the same ratio (27.3%) of people feel distracted and anxious not on regular basis, 18.2% of ratio in chart shows people less than everyday experiencing distraction and anxiety while 13.6% of people do not feel anxious and distracted. 13.6% people were not aware of their distraction and anxiety because of noise and other odd actions done by children.

Examination of closed ended interrogation in survey;

How do you feel bothered and other emotions as whole by child misbehaviors?

Question	n	Always	Sometime	Often	Never	Don't know	Total
1. Have you perceive children behaving in negative way?	22	9.10%	36.40%	45.50%	9.10%	0.00%	<u>100%</u>
2. Have you ever feel bothered when see children behaving in an asocial way?	22	18.20%	59.10%	22.70%	0.00%	0.00%	<u>100%</u>
3. To what extent you feel anxious/restless when child disobeys you?	22	31.80%	40.90%	9.10%	18.20%	0.00%	<u>100%</u>
4. Do you feel uneasiness when child throw tantrums	22	18.20%	50%	13.60%	13.60%	4.50%	<u>100%</u>
5. To what extent you feel your surrounding anxiety causing because of child misbehaviors?	22	22.70%	18.20%	40.90%	13.60%	4.50%	<u>100%</u>
6. Would you feel distract when child will perform hitting and beating actions around you?	22	63.60%	22.70%	4.50%	9.10%	0.00%	<u>100%</u>
7. Would you feel aggressive if child will disobey you?	22	27.30%	27.30%	18.20%	13.60%	13.60%	<u>100%</u>
8. Would you feel your surrounding distract or anxiety causing when children will perform odd behaviors and make noise?	22	27.30%	27.30%	18.20%	13.60%	13.60%	<u>100%</u>

All the close ended questions asked in survey have been assembled above along with the percentage of each question's density and rate of regularity and irregularity of experiences in number of respondents which is represented as "n" in the table chart.

Question 9: Share your any experience when you had felt so disturbed when children was behaving in negative way?

ILLUSTRATION OF RESPONSES	
1: I always face this kind if situation. I'm the second oldest person in my home among my siblings. They often disobey and do misbehave not with me but among themselves while fighting. My younger brother used to do misbehave a lot but my mother always says us to ignore him by saying boys used to do like this. Which is totally wrong. If which should teach manners to our girls then there should be the same rule for girls also. But in Pakistan more then 80% people spoil their boys by just saying they are boys which lead them more freedom to do Morales's things.	10: I have a nephew like he is literally an irritating boy, but I have felt something about him that he is the middle child and I have felt that his parent ignore him and he get lot of punishment from his parents as he does all the attention getting stuff, like teasing his little sister and messing with the things around in house. He many times tried to mess with me as well. Once he put oil on his hair and came to me said paru mamoo(paru as my nick name) take out your tongue and close your eyes I want to perform a magic. Initially I did allow him but then as he insisted I agreed and took out tongue and close eyes and guess what that little disaster did? He put his oily head over my tongue. I scolded him too much...
2: It often happens when there are annoying children around me and specially when their parents don't tell them to behave appropriately	11: I was doing my assignment and my nephew was screaming very loudly as i was a whole day tired so i was feeling so disturbed
3: Don't feel offended ever.	12: Once i went vigorous over my own brother and hit him hard😞😞😞
4: Never Had Such Experience.	13: there is nothing
5: just went away	14: Can't remember
6: I had many experiences when childern disturbed me like when I was working on my assignment and baby of my sister came and start snatching my laptop and toring my papers it was the worst experience of mine	15: I feel distrubed when my cousins or siblings suddenly begin to fight eachother over nothing while playing
7: No experience yet.	16: I don't remember
8: Once i asked my niece to fetch me a glass of water, she was so busy in her tablet that she even didn't listen to me for 3 times. And then i yelled at her, to what she showed up with a negative answer "im not your servant" and i felt so disturbed with this answer.	17: Its my cousin who is 8 years old and sometimes he behave very aggressively and also use i little abusive language with me. I feel so irritated and want to hit him, this way of children should not be tolerated and we should make them learn manners.
9: if children are behaving in negative way shoul b very disrespectful for me as a parents so well upbringing your child you will never disheart with other	18: I felt angry, frustrated and helpless when my little cousin wouldn't stop being extremely loud and aggressive towards everyone in the house because his parents didn't give him attention and this was his way of getting attention. It made me sad for the child that no amount of time or love from others calmed him down.

Other responses were not appropriately defining question that is why they had been left intentionally, the above mentioned responses are based on experiences of people with children and their negative way of behaving and the people who never experienced such incidents. Responses had undoubtedly shown all the results to prove successful results of framework. Most of the respondents had experienced negative behaviors and are having bad experience with children and their way of behaving that gave rise to agitation, trouble, restlessness, frustration and anger also. This question was asked to prove the quality of research question in real life experiences.

Question 10:

How you will try to cope up with such an awful environment?

ILLUSTRATIONS OF RESPONSES	
1: With patience and guiding children with love and if they will not listen then punish them with some tricks that help them to understand the right behavior in a polite manner	8: Firstly u have to deal with this kind of children or this awful environment very patiently...The cause of this Situation is children Anxiety and this disturbance can be the reason of parents shouting towards their children or some kinda of abuse etc... So u dont have to lose your temper...u have to be more careful about these kind of situation... This type of behavior can make anyone disturb but there must be some reason behind this so With calmly u have to tackle all this situation...
2: This all depends on how you grow up a child or in which surroundings they are growing. None of a child learnt to disobey do behave or throw tantrum. This all because of the environment they are living in.	9: I will try to counsel the child. I personally think there is something teasing them most of the time. I will try to give the child some other activity.
3: Stay Calm	10: I'll try to teach children that <u>the should</u> change their behaviour because the way they are behaving is not appropriate.
4: Try to help the child grow.	11: The best way to cope up with the bad work environment is ti trun the workplace with a great way we should do for it
5: I will try to give manners to them	12: Negotiate with children and i'll try to understand them.
6: Ill Raise The Child With Proper Manners And Behavior In Environment	13: I would advise parents to train their children well. And what they do, their children will do. Children always learn from their parents.
7: Will try to make the kid understand things with love	14: I will coach and council the child to the best of my ability or seek professional help for the child if there's no change in his behavior.

This question was illustrated in survey in order to know the resulted behaviors of children misbehaviors. Some people did not responded to this questions and those who did most of them shared their opinion about counselling and teaching f children in order to make them learn moral codes and social acceptancy. Some suggest to make children calm with love and patience, some just left the situation and some even tried to explain misbehaviors as attention getting stuff for children but there is need to compromise with them even if we feel aggressive, angry and mental disturbance.

Conclusion;

The objective of this research was to find the behavioral and mental impacts of child's inappropriate behaviors on adults, but the main focus was to find the symptoms of anxiety in adults when they perceive children behaving in an uneven manner. The survey helped me experience the problem and to reach on adequate results that people suffers anxiety when their perception became physical to misbehaviors. The perception of anxiety causing environment may result to aggressiveness and other cringy behaviors. To some extent everyone experience child misbehaviors as annoying and agitated but the rates may be calculated as different from person to person. This research could help to bridge gap and impacts of child misbehaviors on others along with; it is helpful to grasp the emotional change and to explore physical roles of misbehaviors in producing anxiety in adults. It has been proved by survey evaluation that people suffers apprehensive emotional and physical changes because of pessimistic behavioral exhibition in children. However perception of negative behaviors in children causes apprehension in adult perceivers.

References;

1. Vyner, Henry. (2018). "How Anxiety can lead to aggressive Behaviors & violence." Calm Clinic. Retrieved from; <https://www.calmclinic.com/anxiety/symptoms/aggression-violence>
2. Neylan, M. (1962). Anxiety. *The American Journal of Nursing*, 62(5), 110-111.
doi:10.2307/3418880
3. Sidman, M. (1964). Anxiety. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 108(6), 478-481. Retrieved June 1, 2020, from www.jstor.org/stable/985866
4. Saari, C. (2008). *The Role of the Environment in Psychoanalytic Theory*. *Smith College Studies in Social Work*, 78(2-3), 227–242. doi:10.1080/00377310802111995
5. Morris, R. (1973). Anxiety: Freud and Theology. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 12(2), 189-201. Retrieved June 1, 2020, from www.jstor.org/stable/27505173
6. Guinot Jimeno, F., Yuste Bielsa, S., Cuadros Fernández, C., Lorente Rodríguez, A. I., & Mercadé Bellido, M. (2011). Objective and subjective measures for assessing anxiety in paediatric dental patients. *European journal of paediatric dentistry*, 12(4), 239–244.
7. Graham, George. (2019). "Behaviorism", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of philosophy*. *Philosophy* (Spring 2019 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University.
8. Crosby, J. F. (1976). Theories of anxiety: A theoretical perspective. *The American Journal of Psychoanalysis*, 36(3), 237–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01252989>
9. Carl F. Weems, Natalie M. Costa, Christopher Dehon & Steven L.
10. Berman (2004) Paul Tillich's theory of existential anxiety: A preliminary conceptual and empirical examination, *Anxiety, Stress & Coping*, 17:4, 383-399, DOI: [10.1080/10615800412331318616](https://doi.org/10.1080/10615800412331318616)

- 11.Heshmat, S. (2018). Anxiety vs fear. Retrieved on June 8,2020. From;_ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/science-choice/201812/anxiety-vs-fear>
- 12.Freeman, D. & Freeman, J. (2012). Anxiety, A very short introduction. Ashford color press Ltd, Gosport, Hampshire.
- 13.Shahnaz, R. (2012). An approach to psychology, Bukhari printed press, Lahore.
- 14.Levin, B. (2010). Why are you tolerating your kids bad behavior. Retrieved on June 7, 2020 From; <https://www.sheknows.com/parenting/articles/813642/why-are-you-tolerating-your-kids-bad-behavior-1/>
15. Nieuwenhuys,A, Oudejans,R. (2011). “Anxiety andperceptual motor performance towards an integrated model of concepts mechanisms and processes.” Springlink.com. DOI 10.1007/s00426-011-0384-x

Appendix

The purpose of this research is to examine the rate of anxiety caused by negative child behaviors. Your response in this research would be confidential and data will only be used for this research paper. Your voluntary participation will help us better understand how a negative behavior in children makes other feel disturb. If you are taking part in this research you would have to answer few questions. If you feel uneasy doing it you are free to skip. Thank you for your precious time!!

Name _____

Gender _____

Gender
19 responses

Age

Age
22 responses

1: Have you ever perceive children behaving in a negative way?

22 responses

2: Have you ever feel bothered when you see children behaving in an asocial way?

22 responses

3: To what extent you feel anxious/restlessness when children disobey you?

22 responses

4: Do you feel uneasiness when children throw tantrum?

22 responses

5: To what extent you feel your surrounding most anxiety causing because of child misbehavior?

22 responses

6: Would you feel distract when children will perform hitting and beating actions around you?

22 responses

7: Would you feel aggressive if child will disobey you?

22 responses

8: Would you feel your surrounding distract or anxiety causing when children will perform odd behaviors and make noise?

22 responses

9: Share your any experience when you had felt so disturbed when children was behaving in negative way?

22 responses

10: How you will try to cope up with such an awful environment?

15 responses